

On Some Properties of a Reliability Growth Planning Model

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SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

DoD Directive-Type Memorandum (DTM) 11-003-Reliability Analysis, Planning, Tracking, and Reporting, March 21, 2011 [1], applies to all major DoD developmental acquisition programs. This DTM requires that reliability growth curves (RGC) for such programs be included in the Systems Engineering Plan (SEP) at Milestone A, and be updated in the Test and Evaluation Master Plan (TEMP) beginning at Milestone B. The RGC is to “reflect the reliability growth strategy and be employed to plan, illustrate, and report reliability growth.” Additionally, the Office of the Assistant Secretary of the Army for Acquisition, Logistics, and Technology (ASA(ALT)) issued a Memorandum dated June 26, 2011[2], addressing the subject “Improving the Reliability of U.S. Army Materiel Systems.” This document states that “Program Managers (PMs) of all Acquisition Category I (ACAT I) systems and for ACAT II systems where the sponsor has determined reliability to be an attribute of operational importance shall place reliability growth planning curves in the SEP, TEMP, and Engineering and Manufacturing (EMD) contracts and ensure that U.S. Army systems are resourced to accomplish this requirement.” The ASA(ALT) document stipulates that “Reliability growth planning is quantified and reflected through a reliability growth planning curve using the Planning Model based on Projection Methodology (PM2).” The document also states “Where warranted by unique system characteristics, the Army Test and Evaluation Command (ATEC), in consultation with the Project Manager (PM), may specify an alternative reliability growth planning method.”

Due to the focus on the PM2 reliability growth planning model [3,4] in the ASA(ALT) document, it has become widely used. Recently, an Army organization that wished to utilize an alternate method had a consultant conduct a review of this planning model. A number of properties of PM2 were identified by the organization and their consultant that were deemed to be in conflict with their engineering experience. These properties for the PM2-Continuous Model will be examined in this paper for a large class of problem failure mode expected rate of occurrence functions, which includes the PM2 function. This large class satisfies a set of justifiable, intuitive properties specified by the late Professor Miller [5] for use in modeling the occurrence of new software bugs in reliability growth testing. It will be demonstrated that the

“counterintuitive” properties of PM2 are shared by reliability growth planning models that are based on this large class of problem failure mode rate of occurrence functions. Furthermore, it will be shown that the review’s label of “counterintuitive” for the examined properties is based on a misapplication of the referenced engineering experience associated with conducting a reliability growth test.

1 INTRODUCTION

Reliability Growth (RG) planning is an area of reliability growth that addresses program schedules, amount of testing, resources available, and the realism of the test program in achieving its goals. Reliability growth planning is quantified and reflected through a reliability growth program planning curve. Planning curves typically express a measure of reliability such as Mean Time Between Failure (MTBF) as a function of cumulative test duration and other programmatic resources. The measure of test duration for MTBF is test simulated mission hours. A RG planning curve serves as a baseline against which reliability assessments may be compared throughout the test program. The key features of a planning curve include the following: (1) The initial MTBF, M_I , and the goal MTBF, M_G ; (2) Test phases with MTBF steps over each test phase, where the step represents the benchmark MTBF for the test phase; (3) Corrective Action Periods (CAPs) which are scheduled calendar periods between test phases for implementing corrective actions (termed fixes). Most growth often occurs due to corrective actions in the CAPs, although some fixes may occur in the test phases; (4) An idealized MTBF curve from which the benchmark MTBF steps over the test phases are obtained.

The idealized MTBF curve at cumulative test time t represents the MTBF that can be obtained if all the problem failure modes discovered in test by time t have corrective actions implemented by t . The steps are drawn underneath the idealized curve to reflect an average lag time from when a problem failure mode is first observed to when a corrective action can be physically implemented. More details can be found in [3,4]. To obtain achievable MTBF steps, the idealized MTBF curve should be expressed in terms of achievable input planning parameters that are under the control of the Program Office. PM2 utilizes such planning parameters.

The key planning parameters in the PM2 model are: (1) The initial MTBF goal to be obtained by scheduled and

funded design for reliability activities prior to the growth test developmental period; (2) The goal developmental test (DT) MTBF that supports achieving a successful demonstration of the MTBF requirement with a measure of assurance (e.g. statistical confidence); (3) The developmental test time, T , over which problem failure modes are discovered that are expected to be addressed and implemented prior to or during the last DT CAP; (4) The planned management strategy, MS , defined to be the expected fraction of the initial failure intensity due to failure modes that will be addressed by corrective actions if seen during the DT. Such modes are termed B-modes [3] and are the modes that were previously referred to as problem modes. The remaining failure modes are termed A-modes [3]; and (5) The average fix effectiveness factor expected to be achieved during the DT program. For an individual B-mode, the fraction reduction in the initial rate of occurrence of failures due to the mode as a result of a fix is called the mode's fix effectiveness factor (FEF). The expected average of these mode FEFs is the planning parameter referred to in (5) above.

Section 2 provides several key reliability growth planning concepts associated with the idealized MTBF growth curve. Also the fundamental properties of the B-mode rate of occurrence function, denoted by $h(t)$, specified by Professor Miller [5] are stated and motivated. In Section 3 it is shown how replacing the $h(t)$ utilized in PM2 by any $h(t)$ in a class of rate of occurrence functions that satisfy the fundamental properties, which includes the PM2 $h(t)$, gives rise to a reliability growth model that has the same four properties deemed counterintuitive in the review and which gave rise to the three areas of concern noted by the Army organization. Section 4 contains remarks about the addressed properties based on the facts demonstrated in the paper.

2 BACKGROUND

The MTBF idealized curve mentioned above is generated by considering two types of failure modes, termed A-modes and B-modes. The A-modes are associated with mechanisms that cause failures that are not planned to be addressed by corrective actions. The modes that will be addressed if surfaced in test are referred to as B-modes. The MTBF idealized curve is generated through the following equation for its reciprocal, the rate of occurrence of all failures (termed the failure intensity)

$$\rho(t) = \lambda_A + (1 - \mu_d)\{\lambda_B - h(t)\} + h(t) \quad (1)$$

In the above equation, the $h(t)$ is the rate of occurrence of B-modes at time t . It is also equal to the expected failure intensity due to the B-modes not surfaced by time t . Using this interpretation of $h(t)$, the last term is the contribution to the failure intensity due to these unobserved B-modes. In this equation λ_B equals $h(0)$, the expected failure intensity due to all the B-modes at the start of the first test phase. Thus $\lambda_B - h(t)$ represents the expected failure intensity due to the B-modes that were surfaced by time t . In the second term, μ_d denotes the average planned fix effectiveness factor. Thus, the second term represents the failure intensity contribution due to

the B-modes surfaced by time t after they have been corrected with the planned fix effectiveness factor. Finally, the first term represents the failure intensity contribution due to the A-modes.

An important concept associated with reliability growth planning is the MTBF growth potential and its reciprocal, the failure intensity growth potential. These are denoted by M_{GP} and ρ_{GP} , respectively. ρ_{GP} is approached in the limit as $h(t)$ goes to zero. Thus, M_{GP} can be viewed as a ceiling on the MTBF that can be achieved for a given design. By Equation (1), ρ_{GP} and its reciprocal M_{GP} are given as follows:

$$\rho_{GP} = \lambda_A + (1 - \mu_d)\lambda_B \quad M_{GP} = \frac{M_I}{1 - (MS)\mu_d} \quad (2)$$

These equations and concepts not only apply to the PM2 planning model, but are equally valid for any reliability growth planning model that utilizes an appropriate form for $h(t)$. For PM2, $h(t)$ is given by

$$h(t) = \frac{\lambda_B}{1 + \beta t} \quad (3)$$

where β is a positive scale parameter for $h(t)$.

In Section 3, the properties of PM2 that were reviewed by the consultant will be discussed for a class of growth planning models that are generated via Equation (1) by a large set of $h(t)$ functions. It will be assumed that the $h(t)$ in this class of functions satisfies the fundamental properties advocated by Miller [5]. Miller deemed these properties appropriate for modeling the pattern of the rate of occurrence of new software bugs for reliability growth models. These fundamental properties can be motivated by first considering the exact expression for the expected failure intensity due to the B-modes not surfaced by t , denoted $h_{ex}(t)$. To do so, let k be the number of B-modes residing in the system at the start of the test period, and let λ_i be the rate of occurrence of failures due to B-mode i at the start of the test period prior to corrective actions. It can be shown [6]

$$h_{ex}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i e^{-\lambda_i t} \quad (4)$$

It is assumed that at least one of the λ_i is positive.

Note the following fundamental properties of $h_{ex}(t)$: (i) $h_{ex}(0) = \sum \lambda_i > 0$; (ii) $h_{ex}(t)$ approaches 0 as t increases; and (iii) $(-1)^n h_{ex}^{(n)}(t) > 0$ for all nonnegative integers n , where $h_{ex}^{(n)}(t)$ denotes $h_{ex}(t)$ for $n = 0$ and the n 'th derivative with respect to t of $h_{ex}(t)$ for positive n . In particular, note that (i)-(iii) imply that $h_{ex}(0)$ is a positive finite number and $h_{ex}(t)$ is positive and decreasing towards 0. A function that has property (iii) is called completely monotone [5]. Observe $h_{ex}(t)$ has too many parameters for use in a reliability growth planning model. Thus, for complex systems, a parsimonious approximation to $h_{ex}(t)$ is typically utilized. In the remainder of the paper $h(t)$ will denote any parsimonious approximation for $h_{ex}(t)$ that satisfies the fundamental properties (i) through (iii) above. In addition, it is assumed that the parameters for $h(t)$ include a scale parameter, β , and expected initial B-mode rate of occurrence, $\lambda_B = h(0)$. Note, by definition, β is a scale parameter of $h(t)$ if and only if there exists a function g for which $g(\beta t) = h(t)$ for all positive β and nonnegative t . The

parameter set need not be limited to just these two parameters. However, it is assumed the set of parameters includes β and λ_B , and can be specified independently within their defined parameter domains, in the absence of any imposed conditions other than satisfying (i) through (iii). Also, it is assumed that $h(t)$ can be expressed as the product $\lambda_B\{h_0(t)\}$, where $h_0(t)$ does not depend on λ_B .

To obtain the associated reliability growth model, the parsimonious approximation, $h(t)$, for the expected B-mode rate of occurrence function is utilized in Equation (1). The resulting idealized failure intensity would be used with test phases, specified lag times, and the program test schedule to obtain the test phase MTBF benchmarks and associated metrics as described in MIL-HDBK 189-C [3] for the PM2 $h(t)$ function. The PM2 $h(t)$ function is one member of this large class of $h(t)$ functions.

3 PROPERTIES ADDRESSED IN PM2 REVIEW

3.1 Property 1

The first property, corresponding to the first topic of concern of the Army organization sponsor of the PM2 review, can be paraphrased as follows: Every growth curve will achieve the DT goal MTBF at time T, for any T. This statement is correct from the point of view that as long as the DT goal MTBF is less than the growth potential MTBF, expressed in Equation (2) in terms of input parameters, then one can construct a growth curve that goes from the user input initial MTBF to the goal MTBF in the specified time T with user prescribed values for the management strategy and average FEF. This was one of the model properties deemed counterintuitive by the consultant and will be referred to as Property 1 in the paper. This scenario in which T varied and the other planning parameters were held fixed, forces a tradeoff between T and the model scale parameter β . Here, β denotes the scale parameter for $h(t)$, where $h(t)$ is assumed to meet the assumptions of the class of B-mode rate of occurrence functions described in Section 2.

To address Property 1, let $\theta(t)$ be defined as follows:

$$\theta(t) = \frac{\lambda_B - h(t)}{\lambda_B} = 1 - \frac{h(t)}{h(0)} \quad (5)$$

Observe $\theta(t)$ is the fraction of λ_B contributed by the B-modes discovered in test by time t. Since β is a scale parameter for $h(t)$, it is also a scale parameter for $\theta(t)$. Thus there exists a function $\varphi(x)$ such that $\varphi(\beta t) = \theta(t)$ for all $\beta > 0$ and t nonnegative. Note from (5),

$$h(t) = \lambda_B\{1 - \theta(t)\} = \lambda_B\{1 - \varphi(\beta t)\} \quad (6)$$

From the definition of management strategy for $\lambda_i = (M_i)^{-1}$,

$$\lambda_B = (MS)\lambda_i = \frac{MS}{M_i} \quad \lambda_A = (1-MS)\lambda_i = \frac{1-MS}{M_i} \quad (7)$$

From Equations (1), (6) and (7), one can express the idealized MTBF at time T, $M(T)$, as follows:

$$M_G = M(T) = \frac{M_i}{1 - (MS)\mu_d\varphi(\beta T)} \quad (8)$$

For the scenario for Property 1, the initial and DT goal MTBF are fixed, as is the management strategy and the average FEF. Thus as T is varied, β must vary such that

$$\beta T = C \quad (9)$$

where C is a positive constant for which (8) is satisfied. A unique such constant exists since

$$M_i < M_G < M_{GP} \quad (10)$$

The existence and uniqueness of such a constant follows from the facts that (i) $\varphi(x)$ is an increasing continuous function over (0,1); (ii) $\varphi(0)=0$; and (iii) the limit of $\varphi(x)$ equals 1 as $x \rightarrow \infty$. Thus each idealized growth curve, corresponding to an $h(t)$ from the considered class of B-mode rate of occurrence functions, can be made to yield a specified M_G for every $T > 0$, provided Equation (10) holds. Of course reducing T too far will yield an unrealistically large value of $\beta > 0$ as measured by risk metrics analogous to those considered in MIL-HDBK-189C for PM2. One such risk metric is based on the following fact. Under this scenario, one can show as β increases, the jump from the first MTBF benchmark step to the second MTBF step will be an increasing percentage of the total growth from M_i to M_G . Furthermore, one can show the expected number of B-modes that contribute to this jump will be decreasing as β increases.

It is interesting to consider the original MIL-HDBK-189 planning model [3] whose model equation is shown below.

$$M(T) = \left(\frac{M_i}{1-\alpha}\right) \left(\frac{T}{t_1}\right)^\alpha \quad (11)$$

In this equation, $M(T)$ denotes the DT goal MTBF to be obtained by T. Also t_1 denotes the test time in the first test phase and M_i denotes the average MTBF over the first test phase. Just as for the $h(t)$ scale parameter β , for a specified $M(T)$, the smaller T is the larger the MIL-HDBK-189 growth rate α will be, indicating a higher rate of increase of the MTBF as a function of t. Thus the relevant concern should be whether the inputted values of the five planning parameters for PM2 results in a value of the scale parameter β that is realistic. Does this resulting value of β conform to one's engineering experience and understanding of the current system under development? This is comparable to asking the following with respect to the MIL-HDBK-189 Planning Model: Given current planning parameters M_i , t_1 , T, and $M(T)$ in Equation (11), is the associated value of the growth rate α realistic? In the case of the MIL-HDBK-189 growth rate, one could compare the resulting growth rate to historically achieved growth rates to attempt to assess the risk associated with the planning parameters. For the PM2 Model, one can utilize the risk metrics in [3], as well as any available experience, to judge the plausibility of the β value implied by the input planning parameters.

3.2 Property 2

The second property, corresponding to an area of concern, can be expressed as follows: As the test time T utilized to surface problem modes that contribute to growing to the DT goal MTBF increases, the PM2 model yields the same DT MTBF goal. Engineering experience indicates that as the number of corrective actions increase due to increasing T, the resultant reliability level should increase. This property was noted for the case where the initial MTBF, DT goal MTBF,

management strategy, and average FEF were held fixed, while T was varied. This scenario is the same as for the sponsor's first topic of concern addressed above for Property 1. Such a scenario does not pertain to the kind of engineering experience referenced by the Army organization sponsor, since it leads to a tradeoff between T and model parameter β . Changing β alters the assumed distribution of the B-mode expected initial rates of occurrence (termed the B-mode profile) arrived at by design for reliability (DFR) activities conducted prior to the growth test. This is reflected in the change of the average expected B-mode failure intensity for the B-modes surfaced over any time period $[0, t_0]$. To see this, observe by Equation (6), the average expected B-mode failure intensity for the B-modes surfaced over any time period $[0, t_0]$ is given by

$$\lambda_{B,avg}(t_0, \beta) = \frac{\lambda_B - h(t_0)}{\mu(t_0)} = \frac{\beta\varphi(\beta t_0)}{\int_0^{\beta t_0} \{1 - \varphi(x)\} dx} \quad (12)$$

where $\mu(t)$ is the expected number of B-modes surfaced by t.

However, as for Property 1, it is still of interest to see whether the class of $h(t)$ functions with a scale parameter considered in Property 1 give rise to Property 2 which was deemed "counterintuitive" in the review of PM2. To do so, let $h(t; \beta)$ and $\mu(t; \beta)$ denote $h(t)$ and $\mu(t)$, respectively, with scale parameter β . Also let $T_2 > T_1 > 0$. Note T_i under the postulated scenario forces β_i to satisfy Equation (9) for $i = 1, 2$. Thus $0 < \beta_2 < \beta_1$. Recall $g(x)$ is decreasing for $x \geq 0$ and $g(\beta t) = h(t)$ for all $\beta > 0$ and $t \geq 0$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(T_2; \beta_2) &= \int_0^{T_2} h(t; \beta_2) dt > \int_0^{T_1} h(t; \beta_2) dt \\ &> \int_0^{T_1} h(t; \beta_1) dt = \mu(T_1; \beta_1) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

This shows that Property 2 holds for any planning growth model for the associated scenario whose $h(t)$ is a member of the class described in Section 2.

Note the tradeoff and resulting model behavior is not reflective of the engineering experience reference by the Army organization since the average of the expected surfaced B-mode failure intensities is just a function of the design for reliability activities accomplished prior to the growth test and thus should remain constant across the test period. Holding β fixed along with the planning parameters except for test time T and M_G , one can inquire whether $h(t)$ gives rise to a planning model that conforms to the referenced engineering experience. Note that for this modified scenario, the corrective actions are increasing. To see this, using Equation (6), one has:

$$\mu(T) = \lambda_B \int_0^T \{1 - \varphi(\beta t)\} dt = \frac{\lambda_B}{\beta} \int_0^{\beta T} \{1 - \varphi(x)\} dx \quad (14)$$

Observe $\mu(T)$ is increasing via Equation (14) since λ_B and β are fixed and T is increasing. Thus the number of corrective actions increases as T increases. This, in turn, based on the referenced engineering experience, should lead to a higher achieved value of M_G . This occurs by Equation (8) since $\varphi(x)$ is an increasing function.

3.3 Property 3

The third property addressed in the review that was an area of concern can be expressed as follows: For any time T, increasing M_I increases the expected number of corrective actions to achieve the DT goal MTBF M_G . The engineering expectation of the Army organization was that for a fixed management strategy, average FEF, test period T, and DT goal MTBF, the expected number of corrective actions to achieve M_G should decrease as the initial MTBF is raised towards M_G . This is a reasonable expectation as long as the average failure intensity associated with the B-modes surface over the test period T remains constant, as would be the case during the conduction of a system reliability growth test. However in the scenario postulated by the Army organization, all the PM2 planning inputs except for M_I remain constant. Thus, by Equation (8), this scenario forces β to decrease towards zero as M_I increases towards M_G . This postulated scenario is not reflective of engineering experience associated with executing a system reliability growth test. As shown by Equation (12), the average B-mode failure intensity for B-modes surfaced during the test period from 0 to T is just a function of β and does not change over the test period. However, the postulated test scenario forces β to change, which in turn, by Equation (12), would lead to a changing average B-mode failure intensity for the test period. This postulated scenario in which a forced tradeoff between M_I and β occurs will be explored in this section for the class of $h(t)$ functions discussed in Section 2 that are used in Equation (1) to generate the idealized failure intensity and associated MTBF step reliability growth planning curve.

First, consider an altered scenario that corresponds to engineering experience associated with conducting a reliability growth test over a test period T. In this scenario the management strategy, average FEF, and DT goal MTBF M_G shall be held constant as the initial MTBF is raised towards M_G . To have the scenario be pertinent to engineering experience associated with conducting a reliability growth test, the average expected failure intensity of B-modes surfaced over any test interval is fixed and determined by the design for reliability activities prior to the start of the test. Thus β is fixed. However, by Equation (8), the product βT must be decreasing as M_I is increased towards M_G . Thus the amount of test time T required to obtain the DT goal MTBF is decreasing, in accordance with engineering experience. Also, since T and $\lambda_B = (MS)(\lambda_1)$ are decreasing and β is fixed, the expected number of B-modes surfaced by T is decreasing by Equation (14). This in turn implies that the expected number of corrective actions required to obtain the DT goal MTBF should be decreasing as the initial MTBF is raised, which conforms to engineering experience.

Now consider the scenario associated with Property 3, i.e., all planning parameters are assumed fixed except for M_I . This section assumes that $0 < (MS)\mu_d < 1$. Contrary to what Property 3 states in the review, for this scenario one can show that there exists η_1 and η_2 with $1 - (MS)\mu_d < \eta_1 < \eta_2 < 1$ that satisfy the following: As M_I is increased towards M_G , the

expected number of B-modes by T is an increasing function of $\eta = \frac{M_I}{M_G}$ for $1-(MS)\mu_d < \eta \leq \eta_1$ and a decreasing function of η for $\eta_2 \leq \eta < 1$.

In the following, let $\eta = f(y)$ denote the function that relates η to $y = \beta T$, where $\beta > 0$ is the scale parameter for $h(t)$ and T is fixed. By Equation (8) in Section 3.1 one has

$$\frac{M_I}{M_G} = \eta = f(y) = 1 - (MS)\mu_d \varphi(y) \quad (15)$$

Since $\varphi(y)$ is an increasing function of $y > 0$, η is a decreasing function of $y > 0$. By Equation (15),

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow 0} f(y) = 1 \text{ and } \lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} f(y) = 1 - (MS)\mu_d \quad (16)$$

where $0 < 1-(MS)\mu_d < 1$.

Also note from Equation (8), one has for $y > 0$,

$$\lambda_B = (MS)\lambda_I = (MS) \left\{ \frac{\rho_G}{1-(MS)\mu_d \varphi(y)} \right\} \beta = yT^{-1} \quad (17)$$

For this Subsection, let $\mu(T;y)$ denote the expected number of B-modes surfaced by T where λ_B and β are given by Equation (17). Next, it will be shown that there exists y_1 and y_2 such that $0 < y_2 \leq y_1 < \infty$ for which $\mu(T; y)$ is an increasing function of y for $0 < y \leq y_2$, provided $(MS)\mu_d > 0.5$, and a decreasing function of y for $y_1 \leq y$. Since $\eta = f(y)$ and $f(y)$ is a decreasing function for $y > 0$, it will follow that $\mu(T)$ is an increasing function of η for $1-(MS)\mu_d < \eta \leq \eta_1$ and a decreasing function of η for $\eta_2 \leq \eta < 1$. These values of η are given by $\eta_i = f(y_i)$ for $i=1,2$.

It will now be shown that when $(MS)\mu_d > 0.5$ there exists a $y_2 > 0$ such that $\mu(T;y)$ is an increasing function of y for $0 < y \leq y_2$. By Equations (14) and (17) one has

$$\mu(T; y) = \left\{ \frac{(MS)\rho_G T}{1-(MS)\mu_d \varphi(y)} \right\} \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{y} \int_0^y \varphi(x) dx \right\} \quad (18)$$

Using Equation (18), one can obtain the derivative of $\mu(T;y)$ with respect to y . It can be shown that this derivative is positive if and only if the following inequality holds:

$$Q(y) \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{y} \int_0^y \varphi(x) dx \right\} > \frac{1}{y} \left\{ \varphi(y) - \frac{1}{y} \int_0^y \varphi(x) dx \right\} \quad (19)$$

where

$$Q(y) = \frac{(MS)\mu_d \frac{d\varphi(y)}{dy}}{1-(MS)\mu_d \varphi(y)} \quad (20)$$

Note the limit of $Q(y)$ as y goes to zero equals $(MS)\mu_d L$ where

$$L = \lim_{y \rightarrow 0} \frac{d\varphi(y)}{dy} \quad (21)$$

The limit in Equation (21) exists and is a finite positive number since $h(t)$ satisfies the fundamental properties (i) through (iii).

The limit of the second factor on the left-hand side of Inequality (19) can be shown to equal to 1 by applying L'Hopital's Rule. Applying L'Hopital's Rule to the right-hand side of the Inequality (19) yields $(0.5)L$. Thus as y goes to zero, the limit of the left-hand side of Inequality (19) is greater than the corresponding limit of the right-hand side of Inequality (19), provided $(MS)\mu_d > 0.5$.

Therefore, there exists y_2 such that

$$\frac{d\mu(T;y)}{dy} > 0 \quad (22)$$

for $0 < y < y_2$. This implies, as discussed above, $\mu(T)$ is a decreasing function of $\frac{M_I}{M_G} = \eta = f(y)$ for $\eta_2 \leq \eta < 1$, where $\eta_2 = f(y_2)$. This is in contradiction to the statement of Property 3 in the review of PM2.

Next, it will be shown there exists $y_1 \geq y_2$ such that $\mu(T; y)$ is decreasing for $y \geq y_1$. By Equation (18), for $y \geq 0$,

$$\mu(T; y) = \left\{ \frac{(MS)\rho_G T}{1-(MS)\mu_d \varphi(y)} \right\} \left(\frac{1}{y} \right) \int_0^y \{1 - \varphi(x)\} dx \quad (23)$$

Note that

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(MS)\rho_G T}{1-(MS)\mu_d \varphi(y)} = \frac{(MS)\rho_G T}{1-(MS)\mu_d} < \infty \quad (24)$$

Let $l(y) = y$ and $\omega(y) = \int_0^y \{1 - \varphi(x)\} dx$ for $y \geq 0$. Note $l(0) = 0 = \omega(0)$. Also,

$$\frac{d\omega(y)}{dy} = 1 - \varphi(y) > 0 \text{ and } \frac{d^2\omega(y)}{dy^2} = -\frac{d\varphi(y)}{dy} < 0 \quad (25)$$

Thus $\omega(y)$ is an increasing function and strictly concave. Also the derivative of $\omega(y)$ has a limit of zero as $y \rightarrow \infty$ and a limit of one as $y \rightarrow 0$. Additionally, the derivative of $l(y)$ equals one at $y = 0$. Thus $l(y)$ is the tangent line to $\omega(y)$ at $y = 0$. It follows that

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\omega(y)}{l(y)} = 0 \quad (26)$$

From Equations (23), (24) and (26), there exists $y_1 \geq y_2$ such that $\mu(T;y)$ is decreasing for $y \geq y_1$. As discussed earlier, this implies that $\mu(T)$ is an increasing function of η for $1-(MS)\mu_d < \eta \leq \eta_1$, where $\eta_1 = f(y_1)$.

3.4 Property 4

The last of the four properties in the review can be stated as follows: Using the criterion that an acceptable growth plan should have the DT goal MTBF no higher than 80% of the growth potential MTBF, the PM2 Model limits the use of commercial- of- the- shelf items (COTS) from a low of 0% to a maximum of 70% of the initial system failure rate. In the review the low was actually mistakenly stated to be 38% which is the percent of the initial MTBF to the goal MTBF that limits the use of COTS to approximately zero percent of the initial system failure rate. Also, the DT goal MTBF was taken to be the Initial Operational Test (IOT) MTBF goal. The IOT is a demonstration test conducted by service personnel in simulated mission scenarios after the conclusion of the DT test program. This IOT goal needs to be set sufficiently above the requirement MTBF to be demonstrated during the IOT to have a reasonable chance of being able to successfully demonstrate the requirement with statistical confidence during the IOT. Additionally, the DT MTBF goal is set higher than the IOT MTBF goal, $M_{G,IOT}$, if a drop γ in reliability from the DT to the IOT environment is expected due to more realistic testing, i.e., $M_{G,IOT} = (1-\gamma)M_G$. Property 4 in the review was stated for $\gamma = 0$. The PM2 software characterizes as high risk a ratio of the DT goal to the growth potential ratio greater than 0.80. However this is general guidance, independent of the particular growth model. The fact that the COTS percent contribution to the initial system failure rate must be less than 71% (not 70% as stated in the review) under the 0.80 guidance is independent of the PM2 model. It is shown below this guidance results in the same 71% COTS restriction for a wide class of growth planning models. The allowable COTS contribution also depends on the assumed drop γ and value of μ_d . Although not stated, it appears that the review set $\mu_d = 0.70$, and $\gamma = 0.0$, and assumed the failure modes associated with COTS items were all A-modes and that these modes were

the only A-modes. In general, neither of these assumptions need be true. Under these assumptions, the review results were closely reproduced by use of Equation (28) below. For this case, the portion of the initial system failure rate due to COTS is $\frac{\lambda_A}{\lambda_I} = (1-MS)$. This ratio can be calculated as a function of $\frac{M_I}{M_{G,IOT}}$, by solving Equation (27) for MS:

$$\frac{M_G}{M_{GP}} = \frac{M_G}{\left\{ \frac{M_I}{1 - (MS)\mu_d} \right\}} = \frac{1 - (MS)\mu_d}{M_I} M_G \quad (27)$$

Utilizing the expression for MS, one obtains

$$\frac{\lambda_A}{\lambda_I} = 1 - \left(\frac{1}{\mu_d} \right) \left[1 - \left\{ (1 - \gamma) \left(\frac{M_G}{M_{GP}} \right) \right\} \left(\frac{M_I}{M_{G,IOT}} \right) \right] \quad (28)$$

The only assumptions about the reliability growth model used to obtain Equation (28) are the following: (a) The idealized failure intensity associated with the reliability growth model is given by Equation (1); and (b) the B-mode rate of occurrence function in Equation (1) is a positive decreasing function of $t \geq 0$ with a finite initial value $\lambda_B = h(0)$. Also $h(t) \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. The review did not state the equation utilized to calculate $\frac{\lambda_A}{\lambda_I}$ as a function of $\frac{M_I}{M_{G,IOT}}$. From the above, it is apparent that the “counterintuitive” property concerning COTS ascribed to PM2 is shared by a large class of growth models whose $h(t)$ function satisfies the basic properties described in (b) above.

4 REMARKS

The four properties of PM2-Continuous identified in a review as being counterintuitive were addressed in the paper. It was demonstrated that these properties are shared by reliability growth planning models that are based on a large class of B-mode rate of occurrence functions $h(t)$ which satisfy fundamental properties specified by Miller [5]. The label of “counterintuitive” is based on a misapplication of the engineering experience associated with conducting a reliability growth test. In such a test the B-mode initial rates of occurrence arrived at by up-front design for reliability activities are fixed. However, the implied model parameter trade-offs associated with these “counterintuitive” properties change the implied B-mode profile as reflected in a change to the average of the expected surfaced B-mode failure intensities. The paper demonstrated that if the scenarios associated with these properties are modified in such a way that this average remains constant, then a planning model generated by any $h(t)$ in the class described conforms to the engineering experience referenced by the review’s sponsor.

REFERENCES

1. DoD Directive-Type Memorandum 11-003, “Reliability

- Analysis, Planning, Tracking, and Reporting,” March 21, 2011.
2. H. Shyu, "Improving the Reliability of U.S. Army Materiel Systems," Department of Army Memorandum, Reliability of U.S. Army Materiel Systems, SAAL-ZL, 2011.
 3. MIL-HDBK-189C, “Reliability Growth Management,” June 14, 2011.
 4. P.M. Ellner and J.B. Hall, “An Approach to Reliability Growth Planning based on Failure Mode Discovery and Correction using AMSAA Projection Methodology,” *IEEE Proceedings of the Annual Reliability and Maintainability Symposium*, 2005, pp. 271-277.
 5. D. R. Miller, “Exponential Order Statistic Models of Software Reliability Growth,” *NASA Contractor Report 3909*, 1985.
 6. W. Broemm, P.M. Ellner, J. Woodworth, AMSAA TR-652, “AMSAA Reliability Growth Guide,” September 2000.

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